

Coronal Sealing Ability of Three Temporary Restorative Materials Used in Endodontics: an in vitro Dye Penetration Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: The sealing ability of temporary restorative material is an important parameter for the success of endodontic therapy. Cavit-G and IRM have been widely used for the same purpose. A novel material Orafil-LC, light cured resin based material, has been recently introduced for sealing the access preparations and preventing the microbial re-colonization of root canal system.

Aim: To compare the coronal sealing ability of Cavit G, IRM and Orafil-LC by means of methylene blue dye penetration method.

Methodology: The root canals of fifty mandibular premolars were prepared with Ni-Ti rotary instruments under irrigation with 5% NaOCl and 17% EDTA. Samples were obturated and divided into three experimental and two control groups. All three materials were manipulated according to manufacturer instructions and placed into 4mm deep access cavities. Samples were incubated, thermocycled and then placed in 2 % methylene blue dye for one week. Samples were sectioned bucco-lingually and viewed under stereomicroscope. Degree of dye penetration was evaluated and scored for each group.

Results: Data from each group was compared using one way ANOVA and post hoc Tukey test ($P < 0.05$). Cavit and Orafil-LC showed significantly lower dye leakage than IRM. Conclusion: Cavit and Orafil-LC have better coronal sealing ability than IRM

Keywords: [Dye penetration, Cavit, IRM, Orafil-LC]

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of an endodontic temporary restoration is to prevent the ingress of oral bacteria into the root canal system between the appointments. Leakage of temporary restorations can lead to bacterial penetration of the root canal fill and can complicate the course and outcome of treatment.^[1,2] The quality of coronal seal is as important as the apical seal for the periapical health after the endodontic therapy.^[3] There are various temporary

restorative materials available these with different compositions and setting mechanisms. Cavit-G (3M Deutschland GmbH, Germany) is a pre-manipulated eugenol free, Zinc oxide/zinc sulphate based cement which sets by water absorption.^[4] Together with Cavit, Intermediate Restorative Material IRM (DentsplyDeTrey GmbH, Germany) has been the most commonly used temporary filling material in endodontics. IRM is a zinc oxide eugenol cement reinforced with polymethyl

methacrylate. This reinforcement provides the restoration with improved compressive strength, abrasion resistance and hardness. [5] One of the recently introduced temporary restorative materials is the Orafil-LC (PrevestDenpro, Jammu, India). It is a urethane dimethacrylate based light cured temporary material that can be easily placed and removed from the access preparation. Various methods are available for assessing the coronal sealing ability of restorative materials namely fluid infiltration method, bacterial leakage, dye extraction and dye penetration. [6] Dye penetration has been widely used for leakage assessment studies because of its relative technical simplicity. [7] The aim of this study was to compare the sealing ability of three different endodontic temporary restorative materials namely Cavit, IRM and Orafil LC by dye penetration method.

METHODOLOGY

Fifty extracted, intact, and caries-free human premolars were selected for this study. These teeth were immersed in 5 % sodium hypochlorite (Prevest Denpro, Jammu, India) for 5 minutes to disinfect teeth and remove the soft tissue from the root surfaces. Subsequently, teeth were rinsed and stored in normal saline. The same operator prepared standardized access cavities. Working lengths were determined using K-file size #15 (Dentsply Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) 1 mm short of the apex. Root canal cleaning and shaping was carried out using Protaper Universal rotary files (DentsplyMaillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) upto F3 file. Approximately 2 mL of 5% sodium hypochlorite solution was used for irrigation between each instrumentation procedure. 3 ml of 17 % EDTA liquid (PrevestDenpro, Jammu, India) was used for 1 minute to manage the smear layer. After cleaning and shaping, the root canals were dried with paper points and obturated with Protaper Universal F3 gutta-percha (DentsplyMaillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) and AH Plus sealer (DentsplyMaillefer, Switzerland). When

root canals obturations were completed, a hot instrument and a plugger were used to remove excessive gutta-percha and to ensure good condensation in the coronal part of the root obturation. In this way, a minimum of 4 mm coronal space was available for the temporary restorative material. The teeth were randomly divided into 5 groups (3 experimental and 2 control groups) of 10 premolar teeth each (n=10). The teeth in the positive controls (Group P) were not filled with restorative materials; only a small dry cotton pellet was placed in the pulp chamber. In the negative control group (Group N) cavities were completely filled with inlay wax (BEGO, Germany). In the three experimental groups, all the materials were mixed according to manufacturer's instructions by the same operator. Group A was filled with Cavit-G and it was condensed using a wet cotton pellet. In Group B, IRM was mixed with a powder to liquid ratio of 6:1 and placed into the cavity. In Group C, Orafil G was placed into the access preparation and condensed. Then it was light cured for 40 seconds and excess removed using a scalpel. After placement of the test materials, the specimens were stored in an incubator at 37°C at 100% humidity for 24 hours. The specimens were thermocycled for 500 cycles in distilled water at 5-55°C; i.e. 30 seconds in each bath. [8] After thermocycling, the specimens were air dried. The teeth in the negative control group were completely covered with two layers of nail varnish. The experimental groups and positive control group were also coated twice except the occlusal surfaces. All specimens were placed in 2% methylene blue solution (HiMedia Laboratories, India) at neutral (pH 7.0) in an incubator, at 37°C and 100% humidity for 7 days. They were then removed from the dye solution, washed under tap water, and air dried. A scalpel was used to remove the nail varnish and wax layer. The teeth were sectioned buccolingually using a diamond disc. The samples were then analyzed under 25 X magnification using a stereomicroscope

(Kyowa Getner, Japan). The degree of marginal and surface dye penetration (Table 1) was evaluated according to criteria by Lee et al. [9] Scores were obtained from

different groups and data analysis was done using one-way ANOVA and post hoc Tukey tests (P<0.05).

Table 1: Criteria for the evaluation of the marginal seal of temporary fillings in the dye penetration test (Lee et al.)

Degree	Criteria
0	No dye penetration into the filling material or along the filling-tooth interface
1	Dye penetration into the filling material or along the filling-tooth interface up to the enamel dentine interface
2	Dye penetration into the filling material or along the filling-tooth interface up to the filling edge
3	Dye penetration into the filling material or along the filling-tooth interface up to the endodontic cavity (cotton pellet is discolored)

RESULTS

The negative control group showed no dye penetration (Group N) and the positive control group demonstrated maximum dye penetration (Group P). The mean marginal dye leakage scores for each group are presented in Table 2. In the experimental groups, the lowest dye leakage score was observed in Group A (Cavit-G). However there was no significant difference between Cavit-G (Group A) and Orafil- LC (Group C). Both Cavit-G and Orafil- LC performed significantly better than IRM (Group B) in terms of sealing property.

Table 2: Dye penetration scores of three experimental groups.

Group	0	1	2	3
Cavit-G ^a (Group A)	0	9	1	0
IRM ^b (Group B)	0	0	2	8
Orafil-LC ^a (Group C)	0	8	2	0

^{a,b}Groups with different letters are significantly different (P<0.05)

DISCUSSION

A tight sealing temporary restorative material is paramount to success of endodontic therapy. A good seal between filling material and tooth prevents the ingress of microbes and salivary components into the root canal system thus preventing its recontamination. [10] In the present study, a new light curing temporary material (Orafil-LC) was compared with two commonly used temporary restorative materials (Cavit G, IRM). All of the experimental groups demonstrated leakage within the material. Cavit-G and Orafil-LC showed less marginal leakage than IRM. In the present study, we used a thickness of 4 mm of restorative material because it has been proved that a minimum of 3.5-4 mm of restorative material is necessary to prevent micro leakage. [11] Our study used thermal

cycling procedures to simulate intraoral conditions. The temperature range between 5 °C and 55 °C that was chosen because these were the extremes temperatures that could be experienced in the oral environment. [12] In the present study, IRM showed more leakage than the other two materials tested. This can be due to the fact that the components have to be mixed together to produce the paste and the mixing may be the cause of reduced homogeneity. A study showed numerous voids on the visible surfaces of IRM samples after sectioning. [13] Apart from our study, other past studies have also shown that more microleakage occurs with IRM than with Cavit or Cavitron. [9,14-16] Cavit-G is a premixed temporary restorative material that contains zinc oxide, calcium sulfate, glycol acetate and polyvinyl acetate resins. It possesses a high coefficient of linear expansion, resulting from water sorption. This expansion permits the material to adapt more tightly to dentin walls and providing a good seal under different conditions. [8,16,17] One of the major disadvantages of Cavit-G is its slow setting time. In contrast, Orafil-LC setting process is initiated by exposure to a visible light source. It is a durable light-curing temporary filling material which can be cured upto the depth of 4 mm with tight margins, ready to use, easy to place, and can be removed in one piece with no damage to tooth preparation. Being eugenol free, it has no negative effect on composite bond strengths.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that Cavit-G and Orafil-LC seal against marginal

leakage better than IRM when used as a temporary filling material in endodontic access preparations.

REFERENCES

1. Swanson K, Madison S. An evaluation of coronal microleakage in endodontically treated teeth. *J Endodon* 1987;13:56-9.
2. Torabinejad M, Kettering J. In vitro bacterial penetration of coronally unsealed endodontically treated teeth. *J Endodon* 1990;16:566-9.
3. Ray HA, Trope M. Periapical status of endodontically treated teeth in relation to the technical quality of the root filling and the coronal restoration. *IntEndod J*. 1995 Jan;28(1):12-8.
4. Tennert C, Eismann M, Goetz F, Woelber JP, Hellwig E, Polydorou O. A temporary filling material used for coronal sealing during endodontic treatment may cause tooth fractures in large Class II cavities in vitro. *IntEndod J*. 2015 Jan;48(1):84-8.
5. Anderson RW, Powell BJ, Pashley DH. Microleakage of IRM used to restore endodontic access preparations. *Endod Dent Traumatol*. 1990 Aug;6(4):137-41
6. Verissimo DM, do Vale MS. Methodologies for assessment of apical and coronal leakage of endodontic filling materials: a critical review. *J Oral Sci*. 2006 Sep;48(3):93-8.
7. Camps J, Pashley D. Reliability of the dye penetration studies. *J Endod*. 2003 Sep; 29(9):592-4.
8. Zmener O, Banegas G, Pameijer CH. Coronal microleakage of three temporary restorative materials: an in vitro study. *J Endod* 2004;30:582-4
9. Lee YC, Yang SF, Hwang YF, Chueh LH, Chung KH. Microleakage of endodontic temporary restorative materials. *J Endod* 1993;19:516-20.
10. Naoum HJ, Chandler NP. Temporization for endodontics. *IntEndod J* 2002;35:964-78.
11. Webber RT, del Rio Ce, Brandy JM, Segall RO. Sealing quality of a temporary filling material. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral RadiolEndod* 1978;46:123-30.
12. Hansen SR, Montgomery S. Effect of restoration thickness on the sealing ability of Term. *J Endod* 1993;19:448-52.
13. Deveaux E, Hildebert P, Neut C, Boniface B, Romond C. Bacterial microleakage of Cavit, IRM, Term. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral RadiolEndod* 1992;74:634-43
14. Barkhordar RA, Stark MM. Sealing ability of intermediate restorations and cavity design used in endodontics. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol*. 1990 Jan;69(1):99-101.
15. Kazemi RB, Safavi KE, Spångberg LS. Assessment of marginal stability and permeability of an interim restorative endodontic material. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol*. 1994 Dec;78(6):788-96.
16. Widerman FH, Eames WB, Serene TP. The physical and biologic properties of Cavit. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1971;82:378-82.
17. Tamse A, Ben-Amar A, Gover A. Sealing properties of temporary filling materials used in endodontics. *J Endod* 1982;8:322-5

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